

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND PRACTICE OF ORAL HYGIENE AMONG HEALTHCARE STAFF IN PESHAWAR, PAKISTAN, A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Abstract

Aims: This study aimed to assess the knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) of oral hygiene among health care professionals

Materials and Methods:

A descriptive cross-sectional survey was conducted among 377 individuals, including doctors, nurses, support medical staff, and non-medical staff. A structured questionnaire consisting of 19 items was used to gather data on demographics, knowledge, attitude, and oral hygiene practice. Data segregation and analysis was done on SPSS version 24.

Results:

Most respondents (62.3%) were aged 20-29 years, and 57.6% were male. While 80.1% used toothbrush and toothpaste, only 43.0% brushed twice daily, and 48.0% practiced flossing. Awareness regarding oral hygiene's systemic impact was high (80.6%), yet (45.4%) had never had regular dental check-ups. Significant variations ($P < 0.05$) in oral hygiene practices were observed across professionals, with better habits among doctors and nurses.

Conclusion:

The study highlights a clear gap between knowledge and practice, particularly among non-medical support staff. Targeted oral health education is recommended to improve practices and reduce long-term health risks.

INTRODUCTION

Maintaining an independent life depends on people's capacity to control their regular personal hygiene routines, such as dental hygiene. (1) The state of a person's mouth affects their overall health and well-being. (2) Oral health is a vital complex state that speaks, smiles, smells, tastes, touches, chews, swallows, and expresses a range of emotions through facial expressions without experiencing pain, discomfort, or craniofacial disease. (3,4) A disease-free oral cavity and its surrounding components are considered to be indicators of good oral health. (5) It is vital to evaluate the current incidence of poor oral hygiene practices among the local population, (6) Most oral health issues can be prevented by practicing simple behaviors like regular brushing and flossing, (7) Maintaining good dental health is seen as a fundamental human

right. (8). Maintaining excellent oral health requires knowledge of oral health, especially in developing nations. (9, 10) Health has been linked to aspects of individual knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors. (11) Oral hygiene practices improve oral health education, and additionally, a positive attitude about oral health procedures promotes better dental practices. (12, 13, and 14) this practice is a high correlation between oral hygiene habits and knowledge. Being aware of one's present state of both general and oral health. (15, 16, 17) Dental health is linked to people's knowledge of oral health and proper oral hygiene practices. (18) Good oral hygiene is important for everyone, but it's especially important for health care staff (19, 20) The current literature emphasizes a significant gap between oral health awareness and real hygiene practices, although there are few studies that

specifically address this gap in Peshawar's diverse health care staff. Understanding knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) is crucial for developing successful public health treatments in light of the city's distinctive cultural and socioeconomic environment. The study aims to reduce the gap by scrutinizing the KAP regarding oral hygiene among Peshawar inhabitants. Even though there is much research on oral health in Pakistan, very few specifically target the oral hygiene habits and understanding of the Peshawar health care staff. To evaluate the knowledge, attitude, and practice of oral hygiene among the health care staff in Peshawar Pakistan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out in Peshawar, the provincial capital of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. This research consisted of health care staff Peshawar, and it ensured that data collection was done in a sensitive and respectful way by taking into account the social and cultural norms of the health care staff in Peshawar. The initial step was to get ethical permission from the ethical review committee at City University of Science and Information Technology, Peshawar, Pakistan. A total sample size of the current study was 377 The health care staff in Peshawar, Pakistan, was the subject of the study. Data was collected from the health care staff in Peshawar, Pakistan. All study participants received a self-administered questionnaire form with 19 questions that is designed in English. Every participant receives instructions on how to complete the survey questionnaire pro forma as well as an explanation of the survey's nature and goal. Data was analyzed using statistical software (SPSS) version 24.

RESULTS

This survey included 377 respondents. Males were 217, and females were 160. There were 86 doctors, 83 nurses, 82 support medical staff, and 126 support non-medical staff included. The age is categorized into groups in which the maximum participant was aged between 20 and 29 years (62.3%), the 30-39 age group contains 23.9% of the total sample, 8.8% of the 40-49 age group, and 5.0% of the 50-60 age group.

Summary

There are notable differences when comparing the oral hygiene habits of physicians, nurses, and nonmedical support personnel. While nonmedical support staff frequently employ conventional or unknown cleaning techniques, the majority of participants only use a toothbrush and toothpaste (P

= 0.000). Additionally, there are differences in the frequency of brushing, doctors usually brush twice a day, while many nonmedical professionals only brush once (P = 0.000). All groups brush their teeth before breakfast, although there is no significant difference in this behavior (P = 0.066). Although brushing time is typically 1-2 minutes, there is no significant difference between groups (P = 0.232), and doctors and nurses are more likely to brush after dinner (P = 0.000).

Differences in professional practices are further highlighted by interdental cleaning behaviors. In comparison to nonmedical personnel, doctors floss far more frequently (P = 0.000), and the majority of nonmedical staff either don't use flossing thread or don't know about flossing possibilities (P = 0.000). Doctors and nurses are also more likely to gargle or rinse after meals (P = 0.000). A clear contrast can be seen in routine dental visits: although support staff frequently skip dental appointments unless they are in pain, doctors are proactive with checkups (P = 0.002). Additionally, many support staff members are not aware that toothbrushes need to be changed every three months, although doctors are more likely to do so (P = 0.001).

Despite differences in dental hygiene habits, many habits are shared by all groups. There is no significant difference in the prevalence of tooth sensitivity (P = 0.556) or the amount of toothpaste used (P = 0.172). Nonetheless, sensitivity concerns are more likely to prompt physicians and nurses to seek dental counsel (P = 0.002). There is variation in toothbrush bristle preference; medical professionals prefer soft or medium bristles, while nonmedical personnel are more likely to use hard bristles (P = 0.000). Finally, whereas support personnel had lower knowledge levels (P = 0.000 and P = 0.045, respectively), doctors and nurses have much higher understanding of the systemic impact of poor dental hygiene and the detrimental effects of excessive sweets, alcohol, and smoke.

CROSS TABALUTIONS

Question	Doctor	Nurse	Support medical staff	Support nonmedical Staff	P value *
Toothbrush and Toothpaste	20.42	17.77	18.82	23.07	0.000
Powder	0	0.79	1.06	0.26	
Stick	1.06	1.59	0.53	0.5k3	
Mouthwash	0.79	1.32	1.06	0.26	
Question	Doctor	Nurse	Support medical staff	Support nonmedical staff	P value *
Once	6.10	10.34	8.75	17.50	0.000
Twice	13.5	10.34	11.67	7.42	
After every meal	2.91	1.32	0.79	2.12	
Occasional	0.26	0	0.53	6.36	
Other	0.53	0.53	0.26	9.28	
Question	Doctor	Nurse	Support medical staff	Support nonmedical staff	P value *
Before breakfast	16.71	12.73	14.05	18.83	0.066
After breakfast	6.10	9.28	7.69	14.58	
Question	Doctor	Nurse	Support medical staff	Support nonmedical staff	P value *
Yes	17.50	16.71	15.11	14.58	0.000
No	5.30	5.30	6.63	18.83	
Question	Doctor	Nurse	Support medical staff	Support nonmedical staff	P value*
Less than a minute	1.32	0.53	1.59	3.18	0.232
1 min	6.10	6.89	9.01	10.07	
1-2 min	10.07	10.34	8.48	12.73	
More than 2 min	5.30	4.24	2.65	7.42	
Question	Doctor	Nurse	Support medical staff	Support nonmedical staff	P value *
Yes	15.91	10.61	10.87	10.61	0.000
No	6.89	11.40	10.87	22.81	
Question	Doctor	Nurse	Support medical staff	Support nonmedical staff	P value *
Flossing thread	10.07	4.24	7.69	4.77	0.000
Water flosser	3.71	2.38	1.85	3.71	
Interdental brush	2.91	3.97	1.59	1.59	
Not applicable	6.10	11.40	10.61	23.34	
Question	Doctor	Nurse	Support medical staff	Support nonmedical staff	P value *

Yes	15.64	17.54	12.99	12.73	0.000
No	7.16	4.50	8.75	20.68	
Question	Doctor	Nurse	Support medical staff	Support nonmedical staff	P value *
Once a year	8.75	11.93	6.63	8.75	0.000
Twice a year	6.36	5.57	3.44	3.18	
Never	7.69	4.50	11.67	21.48	
Question	Doctor	Nurse	Support medical staff	Support nonmedical staff	P value *
Yes	18.30	16.44	16.44	19.36	0.002
No	4.50	5.57	5.30	14.05	
Question	Doctor	Nurse	Support medical staff	Support nonmedical staff	P value *
Every 3 months	16.97	16.18	15.91	17.50	0.001
Every 6 months	2.38	2.65	3.44	5.03	
Don't know	3.44	3.18	2.38	10.87	
Question	Doctor	Nurse	Support medical staff	Support nonmedical staff	P value *
Pea size	7.16	6.63	4.59	12.73	0.172
Half of the toothbrush surface is covered	10.34	8.48	10.07	11.40	
More than half of the toothbrush surface is covered	5.30	6.89	7.16	9.28	
Question	Doctor	Nurse	Support medical staff	Support nonmedical staff	P value *
Extra soft	3.18	2.91	1.06	3.44	0.000
Soft	7.42	10.61	11.14	9.01	
Medium	11.67	8.22	8.75	15.11	
Hard	0.53	0.26	0.79	5.83	
Question	Doctor	Nurse	Support medical staff	Support nonmedical staff	P value *
Yes	15.91	16.71	14.58	22.54	0.556
No	6.89	5.30	7.16	10.87	
Question	Doctor	Nurse	Support medical staff	Support nonmedical staff	P value *
Yes	11.14	12.46	7.95	9.54	0.002
No	6.63	6.63	9.01	15.38	
Don't have a sensitivity problem	5.03	2.91	4.77	8.48	

Question	Doctor	Nurse	Support medical staff	Support nonmedical staff	P value *
Yes	19.09	19.09	19.89	22.54	0.000
No	3.71	2.91	1.85	10.87	
Question	Doctor	Nurse	Support medical staff	Support nonmedical staff	P value *
Yes	20.15	19.09	20.15	26.52	0.045
No	2.65	2.91	1.59	6.89	

Discussion

Their higher oral hygiene practices may be explained by the fact that the majority of participants (62.3%) were between the ages of 20 and 29. Of those who used a toothbrush and toothpaste, 80.1% only used it twice a day, and only 41.6% brushed at the suggested time. Due to a lack of preventive treatment, 45.4% of people never went to the dentist. Of those who frequently replaced their toothbrushes, 66.6% did not know when to do it. The results were comparable to research by Abate, B., et al. (2020) among Medhanealem students in Ethiopia. A large number of the population in this study demonstrated positive compliance with regard to the frequency of tooth brushing. According to a study done in Koforidua by Opoku et al, these results are in line with research from Bangladesh, Dhaka Tahazid et al (2022), Zambia, Uganda, and Croatia Kamal et al (2021) that indicated a high degree of knowledge among the health care staff they examined. In our survey, 136 (36.1%) participants said they saw a dentist once a year, 70 (18.6%) said they saw one twice a year, and a noteworthy 45.4% said they never saw a dentist. Although respondents generally have a solid basis of knowledge and positive attitudes. Even though most students had good attitude 91.9% and sufficient understanding of OH 77.2% there was still reluctance to attend the dentist in addition just 41% of subject practiced appropriate OH, the results were comparable to research by Nishika et al, (2024) we assessed dental hygiene habits using these criteria avoid pricking your gums brush your teeth often and rinse your mouth thoroughly with clean water both before and after meals. The results were comparable to research by Michael et al, (2024). Outcome The study founded that more than half 54.1% of the 126 respondents had excellent

knowledge of oral hygiene. Most of them 130 or 55.8% also maintained good dental hygiene the results were comparable to research by percious et al (2024)

And lastly, I give the impression that both the nurse and the doctor are quite knowledgeable. Their cases are in order. Doctors and nurses worry that we don't have these diseases. Perhaps they know more than the average person does. As a result, the doctor and nurse have more knowledge. And it cannot be known to the general nonsupport medical staff who may be cautious. And as a result, it is preferable for the general public to stay informed.

Conclusion

Although individuals in Peshawar have a positive attitude toward oral health, their practices are not sufficient, according to research done among the health care staff. Significant differences in knowledge levels according to education were also discovered in this study, which emphasizes the necessity for facilities for health care centers and focused oral health education programs. The participants in the survey exhibited the highest favorable attitudes toward dental hygiene. When it came to oral hygiene, the majority of survey participants preferred toothbrushes and toothpaste. Overall, the majority of respondents had a favorable attitude, sufficient knowledge, and poor oral hygiene practices.

Limitations

In this study, a small health care staff has been examined. To preserve the health care staff generalizability, extensive research involving a wide range of geographic locations is required. This study is cross-sectional; it only collects data on knowledge,

attitude, and practice at a single point in time with no follow-ups. On this topic, more cohort studies with follow-ups are required.

Recommendations

Planning preventative oral health care initiatives. Encouraging routine or problem-focused dental examinations. Educating the community about oral hygiene through health campaigns. Oral health education initiatives and seminars would be made easier with the use of this data.

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